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BIG FIVE PERSONALITY TRAITS AND TEACHING PERFORMANCE OF FACULTY OF COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION, LAGUNA STATE POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the relationships of big five personality traits and teaching performance of faculty of College of Teacher Education, Laguna State Polytechnic University Los Baños Campus, Los Baños, and Laguna. The study was conducted at the College of Teacher Education (CTE) of Laguna State Polytechnic University-Los Baños Campus during 1st semester of Academic Year 2015-2016 employing correlational research design. The respondents of the study were the 20 faculty of CTE consist of 2 Associate Professors, 10 Assistant Professors and 7 Instructors. A valid survey questionnaire on determining the level of big five personality traits adapted from the site of personality-testing.info, courtesy ipip.ori.org and the IPCR Evaluation are the instruments of this study. Frequency count, percentage and mean were used to describe the profile of the respondents and their teaching performance. Pearson r was used to determine the significant relationship between teachers' big five personality traits and their' teaching performance.

The results describe that teachers tend be about average in most of the big five personality traits except from neuroticism which shows a relatively low description. The results also revealed a weak correlation between variables such that it determined that there is no significant relationship the level of big five personality traits and the teaching performance of the respondents.

Based on the conclusions the researchers suggested to have further study since it is limited only to the faculty of Teacher Education and also it is highly recommended to correlate teaching performance including students' evaluation for their teachers and the academic performance of the students with teachers' personality traits since the teaching performance is one of the factors that affect the students' academic performance.

Keywords: Big Five Personality Traits; Teaching Performance; Relationship; IPCR Evaluation.

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1. Introduction

According to Razak, Darmawan and Keeves, (2009), teachers play an important role in educating the future members of a society through their work in schools. Furthermore, teachers in institutions of higher education, in technical training colleges and in centers of lifelong learning and recurrent education play a critical part in advancing economic and technological development as well as sustaining the well-being of the societies they serve. Consequently, the factors influencing the levels of commitment of the teachers in schools and in the wider education systems must necessarily be the focus of an important field of research leading to the introduction of reform and change within classrooms and lecture theatres, schools, institutions and learning centers, and national systems of education.

Openness to experience is the personality trait of seeking new experience and intellectual pursuits. High scorers may day dream a lot and low scorers may be very down to earth.

Conscientiousness concerns the way in which we control, regulate, and direct our impulses. Impulses are not inherently bad; occasionally time constraints require a snap decision, and acting on our first impulse can be an effective response. High scorers tend to follow rules and prefer clean homes. Low scorers may be messy and cheat others.

Extraversion is marked by pronounced engagement with the external world. Extraverts enjoy being with people, are full of energy, and often experience positive emotions. They tend to be enthusiastic, action-oriented, individuals who are likely to say "Yes!" or "Let's go!" to opportunities for excitement. In groups they like to talk, assert themselves, and draw attention to themselves. Introverts lack the exuberance, energy, and activity levels of extraverts. High scorers tend to be very social while low scorers prefer to work on their own.

Agreeableness reflects individual differences in concern with cooperation and social harmony. Agreeable individuals value getting along with others. They are therefore considerate, friendly, generous, helpful, and willing to compromise their interests with others'. Agreeable people also have an optimistic view of human nature. They believe people are basically honest, decent, and trustworthy. High scorers are typically polite and like people. Low scorers tend to 'tell it like it is'. (<http://www.psychometric-success.com/personality-tests/personality-tests-big-5-aspects.htm>) Neuroticism is the individuals who score high on neuroticism tend to experience effects such as fear, sadness, embarrassment, disgust and anger. Those who score low in this area are usually calm, even-tempered and relaxed at work and in their personal lives. An emotionally intelligent person recognizes and understands the potential consequences of their different emotional states and is able to regulate and control them. Little evidence was found between emotional intelligence and academic intelligence but strong relationships were found between the emotional intelligence dimensions (empathy, autonomy, and emotional control) and the big five, particularly with extraversion and emotional stability (Karen et al, 2002). Schneiderjan et al (2005), however, found strong correlation between emotional stability and academic success in web-based business course. One might argue, in this instance, that students learn better when they are in the company of members of their species other than themselves.

As cited in the study of Rusbadol, N. 2015, previous study supported the notion that there is a positive association between personality traits and teachers’ performance. The findings from one study reported a positive association between nine personality traits such as Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Emotional Stability, Extraversion, Openness, Adaptability, Self-Efficacy, Tough-Mindedness and Work Drive and online teaching performance (Holmes, Kirwan, Bova, & Belcher, 2015).

The Individual Performance Contract and Review (IPCR) form was designed to measure performance of Philippine government employees based on the targets and indicators approved during the Performance Planning/Contracting as indicated in their Individual Performance Contract (IPC) and their field of specialization. The Key Results Area (KRA) in the IPCR includes the instruction, research, extension services, professional development such number of seminars and trainings attended etc., which is evaluated and rated by the deans/ supervisor.

2. Materials and Methods

Correlational research design was employed in this study. The respondents of the study were the 20 faculty of College of Teacher Education (CTE), Academic Year 2015-2016 of Laguna State Polytechnic University, Los Baños Campus, Los Baños, and Laguna. Since the entire regular faculty of CTE is the respondents then total enumerations is applied in getting the number of respondents. Researchers’ adapted survey questionnaires that serve as an instrument of this study in determining the personality traits of the students. Frequency count, percentage, mean, and Pearson r test were used as statistical tools in this study.

This study seeks to describe the respondents’ mean level in terms of big five personality traits and to determine the significant relationship between the said variables and the teaching performance as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Paradigm

3. Results and Discussion

The subsequent tables and figures present the descriptive analysis of the 20 faculty as to their age, gender, specialization, highest educational attainment, designation and performance in IPCR.

Figure 3 shows the teacher-respondents' age. It was shown that there are 2 or 10.0% of the teacher-respondents age 20-29 years old, 5 or 25.0 % age 30-39 years old, 3 or 15.0% age 40-49 years old, 8 or 40.0% are 50-59 years old and 2 or 10.0% are age 60 years old & above.

Figure 2: Respondents' Age

Figure 3 shows the teacher-respondents' gender.

It was shown that there are 18 or 80% female teacher-respondents while only 2 or 20% are male.

Figure 3: Respondents' Gender

Figure 4 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of their position.

It was presented that most of the respondents are Assistant Professors position consist of 11 or 55% while 2 or 10% are Associate Professors, 3 or 15% are Instructor III and 4 or 20% are Instructor I.

Figure 4: Teachers' Position

Table 1 shows the IPCR evaluation of the teachers' performance distributions.

Table 1: Distributions of Teachers' Performance in IPCRF

Range	Frequency	%	Adjectival Rating
4.51-5.00	12	60	Outstanding
3.51-4.50	8	40	Very Satisfactory
2.51-3.50	0	0	Satisfactory
1.51-2.50	0	0	Unsatisfactory
1.50 & below	0	0	Poor

It was shown that most of the teachers which consist of 12 or 60% got an outstanding performance with range from 4.51- 5.00 while 8 or 40% got very satisfactory with range from 3.51-4.50.

This means that most of faculty performs very well which was prove by the results of the data gathered from their IPCR evaluation.

Table 2 shows the mean level of the personality traits of the teachers.

Table 2: Teachers' Mean Level of Personality Traits

Big Five Personality Traits	Mean	SD	Description/Interpretation
Openness	27.1	5.45	About Average
Conscientiousness	30.0	2.80	About Average
Extraversion	30.1	5.15	About Average
Agreeableness	32.4	2.69	About Average
Neuroticism	22.8	4.70	Relatively Low

The mean scores of 27.1 describe the respondents as about average in openness and an SD of 5.45, this results describe that teachers' trait reflects an 'open-mindedness' and interest in culture but the SD describes that there are some faculty who got high scores and low scores wherein high scorers tend to be imaginative, creative, and to seek out cultural and educational experiences while low scorers are more down-to-earth, less interested in art and more practical in nature.

The teachers mean score on conscientiousness is 30.1 with SD of 2.80 which is about average which describe that they are methodical, well organized, and dutiful but sometimes less careful and less focused.

In extraversion their mean scores is also 30.1 an SD of 5.15 which describe that even teachers are sociable there are teachers who prefer to work on their own. This trait reflects preference for, and behavior in, social situations.

Teachers' mean score is 32.4 in agreeableness with an SD of 2.69 describes about average wherein this traits reflects on how an individual tend to interact with others. This kind of traits is really needed by the teachers since high in agreeableness tend to be trusting, friendly and cooperative while low scorers tend to be more aggressive and less cooperative.

In neuroticism, respondents' mean score is 22.8 with an SD of 2.69 which shows relatively low in this dimension. Most of the teacher-respondents' traits in this dimension reflects relaxed, less emotional and less prone to distress and they are not prone to insecurity and emotional distress.

Table 3: Analysis on the Relationship between Level of Big Five Personality Traits and Teacher Performance

Variables	Computed r-value	p-value
Openness & Teaching Performance	-0.059	0.084
Conscientiousness & Teaching Performance	0.006	0.979
Extraversion & Teaching Performance	0.404	0.077
Agreeableness & Teaching Performance	0.373	0.105
Neuroticism & Teaching Performance	-0.219	0.353

Note. $*=p \leq .05$

The value of r is -0.0597. Although technically a negative correlation, the relationship between your variables is only weak (nb. the nearer the value is to zero, the weaker the relationship) and the p-value of 0.084 determined that there is no significant relationship between the openness and teaching performance.

The value of r is 0.006 in conscientiousness and teaching performance determines the relationship between the variables is weak and the p -value of 0,979 determines a non-significance between the variables.

The value of r is 0.4039 with p value of 0,077 relationships between extraversion and teaching performance is weak and the said variables are not significant.

There is no significant relationship between agreeableness and teaching performance with r -value of 0.373 and p -value of 0.105. Although technically a positive correlation, the relationship between the variables is weak.

In neuroticism and teaching performance, the r -value is -0.219 which is describes as negative correlation hence the relationship between the variables is only weak and the p -value of 0.353 determined that there is no significant relationships between the said variables.

4. Conclusion And Recommendations

The results show that all of the personality traits are not significantly related to the teaching performance which means that even they have high or low level of personality traits it does not affect the respondents' teaching performance which is contradict to the findings of research study wherein the findings there was a positive association between personality traits and teachers' performance.

Further study is suggested since it is limited only to the faculty of Teacher Education and also it is highly recommended to correlate teaching performance including students' evaluation for their teachers and the academic performance of the students with teachers' personality traits since the teaching performance is one of the factors that affect the students' academic performance.

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